

Befehle raster calculator

Eignung Pedologie:

ID-Nr.	Beschrieb
107	calcaric, eutric and vertic cambisols, rendzic leptosols
108	vertic and gleyic cambisols, gleyic luvisols
112	eutric, vertic and dystric cambisols, haplic podzols
117	eutric fluvisols, chromic luvisols
119	rendzic leptosols, chromic cambisols, haplic luvisols
121	haplic luvisols, eutric cambisols, eutric gleysols
122	gleyic and haplic luvisols
126	dystric cambisols, haplic podzols
127	rendzic leptosols
200	eutric and dystric cambisols, eutric planosols
201	dystric cambisols, lithic leptosols
208	rendzic and lithic leptosols, partly permanent snow cover
209	dystric and lithic leptosols, haplic podzols, partly permanent snow cover
215	haplic and gleyic luvisols, calcaric cambisols
285	non soils
1000	fluvisols, undifferentiated
2000	anthrosols and urban areas

$$5 * ("ch_soilmap_utm@1" = 121) + 5 * ("ch_soilmap_utm@1" = 209) + 4 * ("ch_soilmap_utm@1" = 127) + 4 * ("ch_soilmap_utm@1" = 200) + 4 * ("ch_soilmap_utm@1" = 208) + 4 * ("ch_soilmap_utm@1" = 285) + 4 * ("ch_soilmap_utm@1" = 1000) + 3 * ("ch_soilmap_utm@1" = 107) + 1 * ("ch_soilmap_utm@1" = 108) + ("ch_soilmap_utm@1" = 112) + ("ch_soilmap_utm@1" = 117) + ("ch_soilmap_utm@1" = 119) + ("ch_soilmap_utm@1" = 122) + ("ch_soilmap_utm@1" = 126) + ("ch_soilmap_utm@1" = 201) + ("ch_soilmap_utm@1" = 215) + ("ch_soilmap_utm@1" = 2000)$$

Eignung Ausrichtung:

Ausrichtung in °, wobei 0° = N, 90° = O, 180° = S, 270° = W

$$\text{if}("ch_slope_utm@1" < 5,5 * ("ch_aspect_utm@1" > 144) * ("ch_aspect_utm@1" <= 218) + 4 * ("ch_aspect_utm@1" > 108) * ("ch_aspect_utm@1" <= 144) + 4 * ("ch_aspect_utm@1" > 218) * ("ch_aspect_utm@1" <= 144) + 3 * ("ch_aspect_utm@1" > 72) * ("ch_aspect_utm@1" <= 108) + 3 * ("ch_aspect_utm@1" > 254) * ("ch_aspect_utm@1" <= 218) + 2 * ("ch_aspect_utm@1" > 36) * ("ch_aspect_utm@1" <= 72) + 2 * ("ch_aspect_utm@1" > 290) * ("ch_aspect_utm@1" <= 254) + 1 * ("ch_aspect_utm@1" > 324) * ("ch_aspect_utm@1" <= 36))$$

Eignung Höhe:

Höhe in Meter über Meer

$$5 * ("ch_dem_utm@1" > 400) * ("ch_dem_utm@1" <= 500) + 4 * ("ch_dem_utm@1" > 380) * ("ch_dem_utm@1" <= 400) + 4 * ("ch_dem_utm@1" > 500) * ("ch_dem_utm@1" <= 600) + 3 * ("ch_dem_utm@1" > 350) * ("ch_dem_utm@1" <= 380) + 3 * ("ch_dem_utm@1" > 600) * ("ch_dem_utm@1" <= 800) + 2 * ("ch_dem_utm@1" > 300) * ("ch_dem_utm@1" <= 350) + 2 * ("ch_dem_utm@1" > 800) * ("ch_dem_utm@1" <= 1300) + 1 * ("ch_dem_utm@1" > 1300) + 1 * ("ch_dem_utm@1" <= 300)$$

Eignung Neigung:

Neigung in °

$$5 * ("ch_slope_utm@1" <= 1) * ("ch_slope_utm@1" > 0.2) + 4 * ("ch_slope_utm@1" <= 3) * ("ch_slope_utm@1" > 1) + 3 * ("ch_slope_utm@1" <= 8) * ("ch_slope_utm@1" > 3) + 2 * ("ch_slope_utm@1" <= 20) * ("ch_slope_utm@1" > 8) + 1 * ("ch_slope_utm@1" > 20) + 1 * ("ch_slope_utm@1" <= 0.2)$$

Eignung TPI:

TPI = 0 entspricht flacher Topographie, TPI > 0 entspricht einer Erhöhung, TPI < 0 entspricht einer Depression

$$5*("ch_tpe_utm@1" > -1)*("ch_tpe_utm@1" <= 1) + 4*("ch_tpe_utm@1" > -5)*("ch_tpe_utm@1" <= -1) + 4*("ch_tpe_utm@1" > 1)*("ch_tpe_utm@1" <= 4) + 3*("ch_tpe_utm@1" > -10)*("ch_tpe_utm@1" <= -5) + 3*("ch_tpe_utm@1" > 4)*("ch_tpe_utm@1" <= 10) + 2*("ch_tpe_utm@1" > -16)*("ch_tpe_utm@1" <= -10) + 2*("ch_tpe_utm@1" > 10)*("ch_tpe_utm@1" <= 25) + 1*("ch_tpe_utm@1" <= -16) + 1*("ch_tpe_utm@1" > 25)$$

Eignung moderne Landnutzung:

ID-Nr.	Beschrieb
1	Continuous urban fabric
2	Discontinuous urban fabric
3	Industrial or commercial units
4	Road and rail networks and associated land
5	Port areas
6	Airports
7	Mineral extraction sites
8	Dump sites
9	Construction sites
10	Green urban areas
11	Sport and leisure facilities
12	Non-irrigated arable land
15	Vineyards
16	Fruit trees and berry plantations
18	Pastures
20	Complex cultivation patterns
21	Land principally occupied by agriculture with significant areas of natural vegetation
23	Broad-leaved forest
24	Coniferous forest
25	Mixed forest
26	Natural grasslands
27	Moors and heathland
28	Sclerophyllous vegetation
29	Transitional woodland-shrub
30	Beaches, dunes, sands
31	Bare rocks
32	Sparsely vegetated areas
33	Burnt areas
34	Glaciers and perpetual snow
35	Inland marshes
36	Peat bogs
40	Water courses
41	Water bodies

$$5*("ch_landuse_utm@1" = 2) + 4*("ch_landuse_utm@1" = 1) + 4*("ch_landuse_utm@1" = 3) + 4*("ch_landuse_utm@1" = 12) + 4*("ch_landuse_utm@1" = 25) + 4*("ch_landuse_utm@1" = 41) + 3*("ch_landuse_utm@1" = 7) + 3*("ch_landuse_utm@1" = 18) + 3*("ch_landuse_utm@1" = 24) + 3*("ch_landuse_utm@1" = 26) + 3*("ch_landuse_utm@1" = 34) + 2*("ch_landuse_utm@1" = 4) + 2*("ch_landuse_utm@1" = 10) + 2*("ch_landuse_utm@1" = 11) + 2*("ch_landuse_utm@1" = 15) + 2*("ch_landuse_utm@1" = 20) + 2*("ch_landuse_utm@1" = 23) + 2*("ch_landuse_utm@1" = 27) + 2*("ch_landuse_utm@1" = 29) + 2*("ch_landuse_utm@1" = 31) + 2*("ch_landuse_utm@1" = 32) + 1*("ch_landuse_utm@1" = 5) + ("ch_landuse_utm@1" = 6) + ("ch_landuse_utm@1" = 8) + ("ch_landuse_utm@1" = 9) + ("ch_landuse_utm@1" = 16) + ("ch_landuse_utm@1" = 21) + ("ch_landuse_utm@1" = 28) + ("ch_landuse_utm@1" = 30) + ("ch_landuse_utm@1" = 33) + ("ch_landuse_utm@1" = 35) + ("ch_landuse_utm@1" = 36) + ("ch_landuse_utm@1" = 40)$$

Eignung Geologie:

ID-Nr.	Beschrieb
1	Alpine
2	Carboniferous
3	Carboniferous – Permian
4	Cretaceous
5	Cretaceous – Eocene
6	Early – Middle Jurassic
7	Early – Middle Permian
8	Early Carboniferous
9	Early Cretaceous
10	Early Jurassic
11	Early Trisassic
12	Eocene – Oligocene
13	Jurassic
14	Jurassic – Cretaceous
15	Jurassic – Eocene
16	Late Carboniferous
17	Late Carboniferous – Middle Permian
18	Late Cretaceous
19	Late Cretaceous – Palaeogene
20	Late Devonian – Late Carboniferous
21	Late Jurassic
22	Late Triassic
23	Mesozoic
24	Middle Jurassic
25	Middle Triassic
26	Miocene
27	Oligocene
28	Oligocene – Miocene
29	Palaeogene – Neogene
30	Palaeozoic
31	Permian
32	Pliocene
33	Precambrian – Palaeozoic
34	Proterozoic – Palaeozoic
35	Proterozoic III – Palaeozoic
36	Proterozoic III – Silurian
37	Quaternary
38	Triassic
39	Triassic - Jurassic

5*("ch_geology_utm@1" = 14) + 5*("ch_geology_utm@1" = 26) + 4*("ch_geology_utm@1" = 4) + 4*("ch_geology_utm@1" = 5) + 4*("ch_geology_utm@1" = 13) + 4*("ch_geology_utm@1" = 27) + 3*("ch_geology_utm@1" = 15) + 3*("ch_geology_utm@1" = 21) + 3*("ch_geology_utm@1" = 31) + 3*("ch_geology_utm@1" = 33) + 3*("ch_geology_utm@1" = 34) + 2*("ch_geology_utm@1" = 6) + 2*("ch_geology_utm@1" = 23) + 2*("ch_geology_utm@1" = 24) + 2*("ch_geology_utm@1" = 25) + 2*("ch_geology_utm@1" = 30) + 2*("ch_geology_utm@1" = 38) + 1*("ch_geology_utm@1" = 1) + ("ch_geology_utm@1" = 2) + ("ch_geology_utm@1" = 3) + ("ch_geology_utm@1" = 7) + ("ch_geology_utm@1" = 8) + ("ch_geology_utm@1" = 9) + ("ch_geology_utm@1" = 10) + ("ch_geology_utm@1" = 11) + ("ch_geology_utm@1" = 12) + ("ch_geology_utm@1" = 16) + ("ch_geology_utm@1" = 17) + ("ch_geology_utm@1" = 18) + ("ch_geology_utm@1" = 19) + ("ch_geology_utm@1" = 20) + ("ch_geology_utm@1" = 22) + ("ch_geology_utm@1" = 28) + ("ch_geology_utm@1" = 29) + ("ch_geology_utm@1" = 32) + ("ch_geology_utm@1" = 35) + ("ch_geology_utm@1" = 36) + ("ch_geology_utm@1" = 37) + ("ch_geology_utm@1" = 39) + ("ch_geology_utm@1" = 40)

Eignung Distanz zu Gewässer:

Distanz in Metern

$$1 * ("ch_distance_water_utm@1" <= 0) + 3 * ("ch_distance_water_utm@1" > 0) * ("ch_distance_water_utm@1" <= 20) + 5 * ("ch_distance_water_utm@1" > 20) * ("ch_distance_water_utm@1" <= 100) + 4 * ("ch_distance_water_utm@1" > 100) * ("ch_distance_water_utm@1" <= 200) + 3 * ("ch_distance_water_utm@1" > 200) * ("ch_distance_water_utm@1" <= 500) + 2 * ("ch_distance_water_utm@1" > 500) * ("ch_distance_water_utm@1" <= 1000) + 1 * ("ch_distance_water_utm@1" > 1000)$$

Eignung Jahresniederschlag:

Jahresniederschlag in mm/a

$$4 * ("ch_ann_perc_utm@1" <= 750) + 5 * ("ch_ann_perc_utm@1" > 750) * ("ch_ann_perc_utm@1" <= 1000) + 4 * ("ch_ann_perc_utm@1" > 1000) * ("ch_ann_perc_utm@1" <= 1200) + 3 * ("ch_ann_perc_utm@1" > 1200) * ("ch_ann_perc_utm@1" <= 1350) + 2 * ("ch_ann_perc_utm@1" > 1350) * ("ch_ann_perc_utm@1" <= 1550) + 1 * ("ch_ann_perc_utm@1" > 1550)$$

Eignung mittlere Jahrestemperatur:

Mittlere Jahrestemperatur in °C*10

$$4 * ("ch_mean_temp_utm@1" > 100) + 5 * ("ch_mean_temp_utm@1" <= 100) * ("ch_mean_temp_utm@1" > 85) + 4 * ("ch_mean_temp_utm@1" <= 85) * ("ch_mean_temp_utm@1" > 70) + 3 * ("ch_mean_temp_utm@1" <= 70) * ("ch_mean_temp_utm@1" > 60) + 2 * ("ch_mean_temp_utm@1" <= 60) * ("ch_mean_temp_utm@1" > 10) + 1 * ("ch_mean_temp_utm@1" <= 10)$$